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Title

Roadmap for the partnerships project within the EU PCP framework

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Publisher

Agentschap Plantentuin Meise

Identifier of the publisher

<https://ror.org/01h1jbk91>

Resource ID

Publication year

2023

Related identifiers

Is it the first time you submit this outcome?

Yes

Creation date

22/12/2022

Version

001

Citation

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Abstract

This report focuses primarily on the procurement framework options needed to support Research & Development within the DiSSCo RI, the Research Infrastructure of the Distributed System of Scientific Collection. DiSSCo will work with both industrial and public partners to co-create services and co-develop products such as, but not limited to, software and digitisation technology and will contract with third parties for goods and services.

The DiSSCo RI will require strategic partnerships with all these actors. A clear strategy allows an organisation to both develop self-sustainability and to align its procurement process with its long term priorities and objectives, supporting partnership development, scaling up, risk mitigation, efficiency gains and building roadmaps.

For this report we build on the efforts of task 4.4 “pre commercial procurement financial structure” of work package 4 “business framework” in the DiSSCo Prepare project. We worked with a technical partner (AcrossLimits) to consider how procurement frameworks have been implemented in other relevant European Research Infrastructures. Through the internal collaboration with other work packages, we gained insight into the opportunities and challenges that pre-commercial procurement (PCP) can represent for DiSSCo with perspective on other procurement types.

This deliverable provides a roadmap for DiSSCo within the PCP framework, leveraging the DiSSCo Strategy developed in DiSSCo Prepare. We do this through offering perspective on funding approaches with their opportunities and challenges for both the DiSSCo Hub as well as its members and funders. We provide an indicative view on the preparation phase to PCP, as this is where the main difference will be found. The execution phases follow a defined approach of execution by the external to DiSSCo innovators, and a judging by the DiSSCo members at each round. We close with a recommendation and final conclusion based on the overall cost and complexity assessment of the considered approaches based on the listed assumptions. These assumptions have to be transferred into DiSSCo Construct, and the model updated where reality turns out different.

Content keywords

organisational

Project reference

DiSSCo Prepare (GA-871043)

WP number

WP4

Project output

Deliverable

Deliverable/milestone number

4.4

Dissemination level

Public

Rights

License

CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)

Resource type

Text

Format

pdf

Funding Programme

H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2

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Roadmap for the partnerships project within the EU PCP framework

DiSSCo Prepare WP 4 – Deliverable 4.4

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Deliverable references

Deliverable	Roadmap for the partnerships project within the EU PCP framework
Work Package	4
Lead Partner	MNHN
Status	DRAFT
Deliverable type	REPORT
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Due date	06/01/2023
Submission date	23/12/2022

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Key words

Commercial Procurement [CP]; Pre-Commercial Procurement [PCP]; Procurement; Public procurement of Innovation [PPI]; Green Procurement; Technology Readiness Level [TRL].

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01 Introduction

Background

The European Research Infrastructure DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) aims to digitally unify all European natural history assets, and to ensure that collection data are easily findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). This will transform a fragmented landscape of collections into an integrated knowledge base, enabling researchers to use and interconnect different collections. DiSSCo represents the largest ever formal agreement between natural history museums, botanical gardens and collection-holding research institutions and universities in the world. Achieving this large goal will require substantial technological effort and innovation, beyond the support of the member institutions alone. Hence, partnerships will be essential to bring the RI into operation.

DiSSCo officially launched its preparatory phase in February 2020 with the DiSSCo Prepare project (Horizon 2020)¹ which runs from 1st of February 2020 until 31st of January 2023, and is coordinated by Naturalis Biodiversity Center, the Netherlands. DiSSCo Prepare will be the primary vehicle through which DiSSCo will raise its overall readiness to favourably and strongly position itself for its construction and operation. Construction preparedness will be achieved by developing a comprehensive Construction Master Plan that will be based on the thorough and complete integration of critical implementation areas. Specifically, DiSSCo Prepare will:

- raise DiSSCo's Implementation readiness level (IRL) across the five following dimensions: scientific, technical, organisational, financial and data. This will enhance DiSSCo's ability to successfully execute construction and effect-related actions based on clear, actionable guidelines with minimum risks.
- deliver DiSSCo's Construction Masterplan. This comprehensive and integrated Masterplan will be the product of the outputs of all of its content related tasks and will be the project's final output. It will effectively serve as the organisational, scientific, financial and technical blueprint for the construction of the DiSSCo RI including establishing it as a legal entity.

¹Distributed System of Scientific Collections - Preparatory Phase Project. Grant agreement ID: [871043](https://doi.org/10.3030/871043) <https://doi.org/10.3030/871043>

Overview of WP4 - business model

A general overview for the business model for DiSSCo as conceived in WP4 can be seen in Figure 1. The associated WP4 tasks focusing on the conceptualisation of the different aspects of the model are indicated in yellow. The model covers aspects of both funding or income and expenditure or cost. The DiSSCo Hub is central in the model, and will act as the central coordination office of the DiSSCo RI, that next to coordination, will also house other functions. DiSSCo services and activities (including financial operations such as running procurements) may be partly centralised in the Hub or distributed. The DiSSCo Hub core activities and products and services will have fixed costs that will be financed through: (1) fixed funds through the national contributions from the Member States (and potential contributions of Observers), (2) variable income from projects, and (3) income from the users of the DiSSCo services.

Figure 1. General overview for a business model for the future DiSSCo RI (source: MNHN).

Relevant for task 4.4 is that DiSSCo has the ambition to be active in research and innovation, to benefit the DiSSCo consortium, as well as other stakeholders, including society. This will be done through partnerships within the DiSSCo consortium and partnerships with third parties that have the capacity to innovate beyond the innovative capacity of the consortium. The task 4.4 relevant partnerships come in different types and flavours in which public procurers (be it the DiSSCo central hub or the separate institutions) buy research and development (R&D) from suppliers in competition with one another (these can be private companies and/or public institutions with R&D capability).

Contribution to DiSSCo

DiSSCo Prepare WP4 aims to prepare a business model for the future DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). This business model will ultimately describe the added value that the DiSSCo RI will bring to the consortium, its users, its stakeholders and society in general, within Europe and beyond. The sustainability of the DiSSCo business model rests on the basic assumption that the value generated by the consortium will match or preferably exceed the public investments by the Member States. Next to public research support, DiSSCo has the ambition to strengthen collaboration with industry to support European R&D and Innovation processes.

Within the many technical challenges that have been identified for the future DiSSCo RI (e.g. Koureas et al. 2018, Allan et al. 2019, Raes et al. 2019, Hardisty et al. 2020, Hardy et al. 2020, Grieb et al. 2021, Glöckler et al. 2022, Petersen et al. 2022), there is a need for **innovation, research and development** that goes beyond the capacities of the DiSSCo partners. Addressing these challenges will require DiSSCo to invest in new technologies and to partner with innovation centres present in the private sector as well as universities and other public research institutions. Insight on what procurement opportunities and challenges lie ahead in working with external partners in the field of innovation will help grow the Implementation Readiness Level and contribute to the Construction Master Plan for DiSSCo.

We believe having a clear procurement strategy for innovation, research and development is essential to create and strengthen both internal and external DiSSCo partnerships. A clear overall strategy enables us to apply a consistent filter to opportunities for development and procurement, in line with the funders vision. When initiating new collaborations, it is widely accepted that “good agreements make good friends”, and “agreements based on shared costs result in even better outcomes.” These principles are further established in the comparison between a prior agreed commitment strategy vs a costly punishment strategy (Han et al. 2013). It is generally accepted that when starting a new collaborative endeavour, it pays to establish upfront how strongly your partner commits to the common goal and what compensation can be expected in case the collaboration is violated. It is shown that when the cost of arranging a commitment deal lies within certain limits, substantial levels of cooperation can be achieved. Moreover, these levels are higher than that achieved by simple costly punishment, especially when one insists on sharing the arrangement cost.

Aims of Task 4.4

Task 4.4 considers and evaluates the potential benefits of standard Commercial Procurement (CP), Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) for DiSSCo. Specifically in relation to the procurement of research and innovation, CP can be ruled out; although in the wider context of general purpose procurement, CP will find a role. We need to consider the utility of PCP and PPI, and any potential benefits they may represent. PCP is defined as procurement of **R&D services**. PCP focuses on the R&D phase before wide commercialisation. PPI is similar to PCP but relates to scale-up activities for market-ready innovations rather than R&D risk-sharing.

The present report builds on DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 4.4 (Pijls et al. 2022), where we provided insight into the opportunities that public procurement, specifically PCP and PPI, could represent for DiSSCo. Those insights stem from the efforts completed during the DiSSCo Prepare project and the internal collaboration with other work packages. Also, DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 8.4 (French et al. 2021), provided background for this deliverable, through a broad overview of procurement types to manage partnerships with industrial stakeholders. It also considered how procurement frameworks have been implemented in other relevant European Research Infrastructures. In particular, French et al. (2021) looked at procurement from three perspectives, being strategic partnerships and co-creation, a legal framework supporting procurement and the Green procurement policy. The EU has introduced the principle of Green Public Procurement as a voluntary instrument (Figure 2), which considering its scope, we feel DiSSCo should incorporate.

Figure 2. Environmental impact of EU consumption using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Source: <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/lcProjects.html>)

02 Pre-Commercial Procurement

Standard public procurement

All legal entities use procurement. Standard (commercial) procurement processes apply to market ready products and services and is, at its root, synonymous with buying; however, procurement entails more than a mere financial transaction. Procurement assumes that a set of formal decisions have been made in the selection of what it is that will be purchased and that a predefined process has been followed in order to demonstrate that best value for money has been achieved, amongst other things. Most commercial organisations follow a formalised process and all public entities and the majority of publicly funded entities are required to do so. This so-called public procurement process is the sequence of activities starting with the assessment of needs through awards to contract management and final payment, whereby public authorities - including government and public agencies - buy goods and services. In fact procurement processes for public entities are mandated in EU and national laws and are governed by strictly enforced regulations. They make up a considerable proportion of the European Union market².

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has established that public procurement is at the centre of innovation policy initiatives (Salomó et al. 2013, OECD 2017). Governments have large purchasing power, and can therefore pull demand for innovation (Mazzucato 2019). For example, the EU has made procurement a cornerstone of its digital strategy, implementing many directives that relate to public procurement. Guidance about EU public procurement and links to the relevant directives can be found on YourEurope³.

Additionally, there are specialised legal entities that provide advice regarding national implementations of the EU public procurement directives, one such entity is the online platform: The International Comparative Legal Guide⁴ where EU member state guidance⁵ can be found.

Pre-Commercial Procurement and Public Procurement of Innovation

To boost innovation in the EU single market⁶, the concepts of pre-commercial procurement (PCP) and public procurements of innovation (PPI) have been defined, developed and deployed (EU 2022). From D4.2⁷, we learn that while ERICs are generally incited to develop partnerships with public and private entities that increase both their visibility and sustainability, one ERIC underlines the risk of interference of the partner into the ERIC management. A consequence is the rejection of private fundings by the ERIC to ensure full independence and total control of its data (Lymer, 2022). In the case of PCP, the partnership with non-DiSSCo entities (private and/or public) will be housed within the PCP framework, meaning that external partners will not have the possibility to enter into the ERIC, providing an additional protective measure to the sustainable development of DiSSCo-ERIC. PPI and PCP are complementary (Figure 3). PCP is defined as procurement of **R&D services** involving risk-benefit sharing under market conditions⁸ and competitive development in

² <https://innovation-procurement.org/>

³ https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/selling-in-eu/public-contracts/public-tendering-rules/index_en.htm

⁴ <https://iclg.com/compare>

⁵ https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/tools-public-buyers/public-procurement-eu-countries_en

⁶ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/public-procurement_en

⁷ DiSSCo Prepare WP 4 – Deliverable 4.2, Report on ERICs financial activities and commissioned services

⁸ Risk-benefit sharing under market conditions refers to the PCP approach in which procurers share with suppliers at market price the risks and the benefits related to the IPR resulting from the R&D.

phases⁹. PCP focuses on the R&D phase before wide commercialisation. PPI is similar to PCP but relates to scale-up activities for market-ready innovations rather than R&D risk-sharing. While in PCP goods or services are not available in the market, a PPI starts in cases that are closer to the market. Therefore, PCP and PPI must be employed in different circumstances, as outlined below.

PCP addresses specifically the procurement of research and development (R&D) services rather than actual goods and services, and can be used if there are no near-to-the-market solutions and new R&D is needed. In the PCP process advantages and disadvantages of alternative competing solutions are compared, and in this way the risks and benefits are shared (EU 2022) (Figure 3). PCP thus induces a win-win for commercial suppliers of R&D and public procurers, and in addition also provides a benefit for the broader society (Salomó et al. 2013, Cappellato et al. 2016).

PPI has been developed to enable the upscaling of innovative solutions. It is a public procurement procedure where contracting public authorities act as initial buyers or customers of innovative goods or services which are in a near-market phase or already available on a small-scale commercial basis (Edquist et al. 2015, OECD 2017). Thus, the important difference with PCP is that PPI can be used when challenges can be addressed by innovative solutions that are nearly or already in small quantities on the market and don't need new R&D (Milenković et al. 2022).

Figure 3. PCP and PPI in the TRL order (source: <https://carematrix.eu/pcp-process/>)

The purchase of innovative goods and services by public authorities can be regarded as a means of improving Europe’s economic competitiveness while helping to solve societal and environmental problems or deliver more efficient public services (Edquist & Zabala-Iturriagagoitia 2012, Rolfstam 2013, Turkama et al. 2012, Rigby 2013, 2016, Milenković et al. 2022). In addition, public procurement can help promote market uptake of innovative products and services, and at the same time raise the quality of public services (Edler & Uyarra 2013).

⁹ Competitive development in phases refers to the competitive approach to buy the R&D from several competing R&D providers in parallel and to compare and identify the best value for money solutions on the market to address the PCP challenge. To reduce the investment risk for the procurer, reward the most competitive solutions and facilitate the participation of smaller innovative companies, the R&D is also split into phases (solution design, prototyping, original development and validation / testing of the first products), with the number of competing R&D providers being reduced after each phase

Both schemes reward publicly funded entities for creating opportunities for innovation in the EU marketplace. Herein, innovative partnerships enable the contracting authorities to pull industrial R&D capacity towards its needs and foster innovation in the public sector (Sørensen & Torfing 2012, Carbonara & Pellegrino 2020). In fact, the EU has made public procurement a driver of its strategy to harmonise the European Single Market. To help publicly funded organisations, new to this way of working, the EU has launched funding schemes¹⁰ designed to help them understand and practise PCP/PPI activities.

The PCP/PPI process is complicated yet it is considerably more accessible than using a standard public procurement for the same exercise (Salomó et al. 2013, Milenković et al. 2022). Simplification has been made possible through the contexts explicitly described in the names themselves: Pre-Commercial and Innovation. The term pre-commercial defines an activity that is adjacent to marketplace activity, not within it. Innovation defines an activity that is novel and seeking to enter a market. These justifications result in PCP and PPI not being classified as commercial activities; hence, there are no competitive elements to consider when judging fairness issues. Notwithstanding this observation, the PCP/PPI process can appear relatively complex at first and the rules that govern their use impose specific requirements (Milenković et al. 2022). Effectively, the rules of PCP and PPI define a process that begins with an idea and confirmation of a novel need, all the way to a current best available solution.

The PCP Process Model is illustrated in Figure 4, including the PPI Process Model, which is further simplified to follow a PCP or run independently. The figure illustrates how PCP and PPI represent additional steps on the standard Commercial Procurement process. These steps are only relevant if the market consultation proves that PCP or PPI are applicable.

Figure 4. Schematic overview of the PCP Process, including the PPI Process (in green), and Commercial Procurement (in red).

¹⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/horizon-europe-funding-pcp-and-ppi>

The successive steps in the model are explained in more detail below:

1. **Organisation Administration.** The structures and processes that manage an organisation.
2. **Organisation Strategy.** The organisation's needs and direction that filter ideas and define the rules and constraints that govern the planning process in short-, medium- and long-term goals.
3. **Capability Gap Analysis.** The comparison between a project and the organisational characteristics, capabilities and capacities. Identified gaps that need to be filled or bridged before the plan can be executed help set a business case within a cost/benefit analysis.
4. **Business Case.** Next to the strategic fit and purpose, a business case covers the plan for addressing gaps and argumentation for executing a project. The business case will include a description of the means by which the project will be executed along with a credible implementation plan to integrate it within the organisational structures and processes. The consortium identifies a specific challenge in the innovation pipeline with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). All this will be presented to a decision-making body for a go/no-go/reloop decision.
5. **Market Consultation.** If the decision body decides to proceed, a market survey must be carried out using a prior information notice (PIN), in order to determine if identified gaps can be filled by existing products and/or services. If suitable mature products and/or services are found then a standard procurement process is followed. If novel, immature products and/or services are found then a PPI process should be followed. If no suitable products and/or services are found then a PCP process can be followed to develop them. As support, the EU provides guidance and funding. The funding can be split between the preparation stage and the execution stage. The EU considers the open market consultation as eligible activities to allocate to the preparation stage of a PCP action. The outcome and gained perspective will contribute to the final tender specification.
6. **Competition Design.** The point of PCP is effectively to ask a range of entities to design and develop something for you. Therefore, this something needs to be specified in sufficient detail in the contract notice for potential competing innovators to build convincing tenders. Additionally, the process of the competition and its rules must form part of the call, so that tenderers understand your decision logic.
7. **Call for Tenders.** Once the competition is designed, the detailed tender specifications must be verified with the board. Only when approval has been granted can the Call for Tenders be published.
8. **Select Candidates.** The call for tenders will include a closing date. At some time after the closing date, the tenders will be opened (also specified in the call for tenders) and reviewed. From the tenders submitted, a sifting action by the project team has to identify those that meet the tender specifications. From these, an amount to assure a successful competition should be selected. Those selected will be formally notified and requested to confirm their interest in pursuing the competition.
9. **Run PCP Competition:** Typical R&D stages are the Solutions Design, Prototyping and Original Development and Operational Testing. After each round, select the proposals that best meet the success criteria, eliminate those that do not meet success criteria and fill the quota of that round. Continue until there are only solutions left that meet the success criteria. The entities behind the final solution(s) are the competition winner(s) and may be selected to develop their results into a market ready product or service. Alternatively, the developed solutions may be taken to another competition where a PPI is run to identify candidate entities able to develop the results into a market ready product or service. The EU considers some preparation and executing efforts as eligible activities to allocate to the execution stage of a PCP action (Figure 9).
10. **Run Standard Purchase Process:** Once the lead solution notifies the tendering organisation that their product/service is market ready, a standard commercial procurement process can begin.

03 Methodology

We studied the suitability of different procurement strategies (including standard public commercial procurement, PCP and PPI) for DiSSCo, and evaluated how DiSSCo can leverage them.

As a first step, we conducted surveys for procurement awareness within the DiSSCo consortium and to get a view on currently already considered development needs. Details on these surveys are provided in the milestone document MS4.4 (Pijls et al. 2022).

We then upheld the development needs against the following criteria:

- What is the relevance for DiSSCo and does it fit within the DiSSCo strategic programme and construction programme (Hardisty et al. 2020, Alonso & Koureas 2021, Petersen et al. 2022)?
- What is the novelty or Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the proposed development need?
- Can the development proposal be executed within DiSSCo by its members, or is there a need for an external partnership?
- Which procurement framework¹¹ fits best for the given development proposal (PCP, PPI, CP)?

To further detail the strategic relevance per development proposal, we presented the topics for PCP to the CSO. Together with the technical audience in the second all-hands meeting (AHM2 2022), we considered the TRL's and needs for external partnerships. We illustrated which procurement structures are relevant to DiSSCo developments to the fourth funders forum (FF4 2022).

From the CSO, we gathered insight on the 4 DiSSCo strategic pillars, being:

- Digitisation, to accelerate and lower barriers for digitisation across European Natural History Collections.
- Access, to create, measure and support multimodal standardised routes to access collections
- Capacity Building, to ensure users and partners are confidently supplying/using data through DiSSCo and are making use of DiSSCo's services
- e-Services for the development of e-Services based on user needs defined through engaging with our stakeholders

This, combined with the result of the AHM2 workshop on PCP, helped us to establish that even at the Prepare stage, DiSSCo shows potential for pre-commercial procurement.

We created awareness of these findings at the 4th Funders Forum, after which we compiled our findings and published them in an internal Milestone document (MS4.4) (Pijls et al. 2022).

In parallel, we had access to the expertise of AcrossLimits and procurement examples and analysis in agreement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which were valuable resources to progress. In this regard DiSSCo and the domain of Biodiversity information is one of the case studies towards the implementation and sustainability of the EOSC in the future (Mergen et al. 2022, Roi et al. 2022). This resulted in a mutual benefit for both sides. Further analyses and identification of the most relevant scenarios made use of several resources, documents and examples of procurement provided by the European Commission. We analysed existing procurement examples such as:

- EOSC Procurement - Preliminary Market Consultation Report¹²
- The PREFORMA project PCP (2017) Towards a sustainable ecosystem for long term digital preservation of cultural heritage¹³.

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-13-general-annexes_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/open-market-consultation-european-open-science-cloud-public-procurement-action>

¹³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/towards-sustainable-ecosystem-long-term-digital-preservation-cultural-heritage>

- The Archiver Pilot on Archiving and preservation for research environments (June 2022) which is in its PCP end-phase¹⁴ and the very clear and informative slide deck documenting the whole PCP process¹⁵

We compiled our learning in an indicative model, based on principle thinking as no reference data was found on the cost and complexity within a consortium during the preparation and execution of a PCP. This model is addressed in the perspective section (Section 5), in which both cost and complexity are projected using assumptions and business logic to see how they vary between the different procurement options for the Hub as well as the members of DiSSCo.

Figure 5. Mass digitisation of specimens in liquid and of anatomical structures poses significant technological challenges and have been identified as development needs for the future DiSSCo RI. The photographs represent some examples: a) Snakes preserved in liquid (image courtesy Royal Museum for Central Africa), b) Economic botany collection preserved in jars (image courtesy Meise Botanic Garden), c) Gallery of comparative anatomy (image courtesy, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Bernard Faye)

¹⁴ <https://www.archiver-project.eu/archiver-pilot-end-phase-event>

¹⁵ https://www.archiver-project.eu/sites/default/files/Archiver_PilotEndPhase_SingleSlide.pdf

04 Opportunities

Procurement opportunities for the future DiSSCo RI

In order to gain insights on which strategic programmes foresee development needs, either in-house or via external partners, and would eventually engage in some kind of procurement, a survey was completed by 3 WP's leaders (representing the WP's Human Resources, Training and Users Support, Capacity Enhancement and Common Resources & Standards) and 10 individuals representing 1 or more DiSSCo Prepare tasks.

Their answers enabled us to locate where PCP might be applicable and drill deeper into those opportunities. For some tasks no new development was foreseen. In others, there was uncertainty at the time of the survey, and in four tasks, the representatives indicated that development was foreseen in the (near) future. Most of them saw in-house development as the way forward. However, in three tasks (T2.2¹⁶, T3.2¹⁷ and T6.3¹⁸) there was a clear indication for a need for collaboration with external partners through procurement.

Further insights on which development needs would benefit from PCP, PPI or CP were gained during a session on the 2nd DiSSCo prepare all-hands-meeting. This resulted in **three well-defined development needs** for which there is PCP potential:

- **Mass Digitisation of specimens stored in liquid** and of **anatomical structures** (Figure 5)
- **A cloud-based Collection Management System (CMS)** using **FAIR Digital Objects**
- **Data Enhancing Annotation and Curation** through **machine learning/experts**.

It should be noted that the results of this survey and further insights are not to be regarded as final, as it is reasonable to assume that additional development needs will emerge in the future. On top, digitisation technologies, data management systems and machine learning are fast evolving fields, in which continuous development will be needed.

Comparing possible procurement scenarios

Regardless of the type of the procurement employed (Standard, PCP, or PPI) we now consider how procurement services might be deployed within DiSSCo. Considering the nature of the DiSSCo organisation (regardless of its legal form), there will be some form of a central core ("Central hub", for example in the case of an ERIC), likely with a number of member organisations around it. Within this context we considered four possible models for the "DiSSCo procurement office".

Procurement activities can be organised through different models (Figure 6). In large commercial organisations it is often organised centrally and run as a cost centre in the business core. However, in a partner led organisation, the centralised procurement function could be delegated to one of the partners, possibly on a rotating basis like the EU presidency. It is also possible for procurement activities to be undertaken in a distributed manner, where small entities, which share similar requirements in the product/service they wish to procure, get together to save costs. Such a distributed organisation can be difficult and time-consuming to manage, especially if partner requirements start to drift during the specification stage. The organisation of distributed

¹⁶ Task 2.2 Helpdesk and user support services

¹⁷ Task 3.2 Collate, refine and implement best practices for data mobilisation at the institutional level to develop the DiSSCo plan for data mobilisation and curation pipelines

¹⁸ Task 6.3 Technical interface requirements of the end-user services

procurement can be conducted on an ad hoc, project by project or contract by contract basis, or it can be semi-formalised through the creation of a networked procurement “cluster”, where some level of structure is established.

It is the choice of institutes within the same Member State to appoint a national hub that reports into the DiSSCo hub, or for its institutes to report directly into the DiSSCo Hub.

Figure 6. Possible DiSSCo Procurement Office Models.

When looking in more detail at the models in figure 6, the following can be deduced:

- **Centralised Dedicated model**
 - Procurement is executed as an integral part of the central DiSSCo organisation.
 - It is composed of resources at the DiSSCo Hub, on the payroll or contracted.
 - Inherently it subscribes to the DiSSCo strategy
 - Information build up leads to expertise growth in a formal structure
- **Centralised Delegated**
 - Procurement is executed as an outsourced part of the central DiSSCo organisation.
 - It is delegated to procurement resources from a single member organisation.
 - There is a mid-term horizon and therefore ideally a level of shared strategy.
 - Information exchanged during a period of expertise growth at the single member.
- **Distributed Networked**
 - Procurement is executed by collaborating offices on a semi-formalised basis.
 - It is a combination of different procurement teams in partner organisations.
 - There is a level of ongoing collaboration and (best) some strategic alignment.
 - Limited information is exchanged as some fragmented (in)formal structures develop.
- **Distributed Ad Hoc**
 - Procurement is executed by collaborating offices on a project by project basis.
 - It is composed of ad hoc efforts by diverse procurement teams across members.
 - There is no long-term collaboration and therefore no strategic alignment.
 - Information is exchanged on a needs basis and no (in)formal structures develop.

05 Perspective

Procurement Office models differ in Cost and Complexity for DiSSCo and its members

There is an overall cost and complexity associated with each procurement approach and the significance of these will differ depending upon the point of view (DiSSCo Hub or DiSSCo Member perspective). For this reason, we developed a simplified model that considered the costs and complexity associated with each procurement approach, from both perspectives (Figure 7).

The PCP and PPI schemes have not seen the uptake anticipated by the EC. More recently, to support the roll out of the Digital Strategy, steps have been taken to encourage experimentation with PCP and PPI in the public sector. To this end, the EC has published calls inviting public bodies and publicly funded bodies. It has not been possible to locate any current open calls but examples of successful projects in the ICT domain¹⁹ exist and future calls²⁰ will be revealed in future work programmes for Horizon Europe. However, it should be noted that these calls are domain specific and it cannot be guaranteed that future calls will accommodate the DiSSCo domain, similar as the non-ICT domain PCP and PPI calls funded during H2020²¹.

In the proposal, the consortium shall already identify a specific challenge in the innovation plans of the procurers that requires innovation and the relevant Key Performance Indicators (targeted quality/efficiency improvements) for the PCP/PPI. If the proposal is accepted, the EU funding is split between the eligible activities of completion of the preparation stage and the execution stage. A rule that needs to be respected is that at least 50% of the funding needs to be allocated to the actual procurement of R&D. The EU considers the open market consultation as an activity that is eligible for funding and considers it as part of the preparation stage of a PCP action. The outcome and gained perspective will contribute to the final tender specification.

The principle based model is not data driven as none was found during several internet searches performed by our partner, AcrossLimits. We adopted an index approach, estimating values associated with each model relative to each other. The number represents a value above or below a normative value which is determined to represent the value for the service in the reference scenario, being the distributed ad hoc approach: this value is represented by 100, it can be exceeded or not reached. These indices are derived only from the experience and logic of the authors and are to be validated with the CSO and the Funders. The index values assume the distributed ad hoc procurement as baseline (Figure 7), as it is the default mode if no proactive thought is put into organising procurement for DiSSCo.

Cost is the spending of resources, time and effort. If a large amount of work needs to be done by the DiSSCo hub, this will translate into a larger cost. Complexity is understood as the state of having many parts and being difficult to understand or find an answer to. If this effort is large but clear, with little chance of reloops and little need for micro management, the complexity is lower. To illustrate, a dedicated resource, while costly and hard working, will reduce the complexity, as the level of expertise and confidence is high. For a distributed ad hoc approach, the total effort will be larger, as the expertise and confidence is missing, so while the overall cost is distributed across all members, the overall complexity is significantly higher, which in turn can add to the amount of effort.

¹⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/pcp-and-pi-projects>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/horizon-europe-funding-pcp-and-ppi>

²¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/non-ict-eu-funded-innovation-procurement-projects>

comparing DiSSCo's possible procurement structures

Figure 7. Indicative relative comparison values for the DiSSCo Procurement models shown in Figure 6 (index 100 = distributed ad hoc approach)

The Assumptions

To be able to make an analysis, we have to make some starting assumptions with regards to who covers the procurement resources, and what impact this represents. In our interaction with the Funders Forum, which was mainly a sharing-of-info one, we did not get to a level of interaction where we could address validation of our assumptions.

The assumptions are:

- For Centralised Dedicated:
 - The DiSSCo Hub dedicates resources
 - This enables expertise to build up over time and a Single Point of Contact for awareness of where to go for the DiSSCo members.
 - Advantages found in having someone present in the hub, such as the strategy awareness, responsiveness and approachability. (note: any organisational burden of an extra Full Time Equivalent (FTE) is to be considered, even if outsourced, albeit in another topic than procurement)
 - The complexity for the hub consists of contacting all members, retrieving input and following up on it, as well as compiling the required documents and executing steps.
 - The complexity for all members is reduced to providing input upon request
- For Centralised Delegated:
 - The cost of resources at the appointed member will be carried over to the Hub, while the cost for the members remains the same as in the centralised dedicated approach.
 - Efficiency gains through temporary²² expertise building and temporary Single Point of Contact for both the hub and the members
 - Here it is the Delegated Single Point of Contact that will be contacting all members for input and following up on it, as well as compiling the required documents and executing steps.
 - The complexity for the hub consists of connecting to the delegated Single Point of Contact.
 - The complexity for all members is reduced to providing input upon request

²² temporary as for the delegated approach we assume defined periods of time before the burden is delegated to a next member, this is in line with the spirit of widening the PCP experience within the public domain, however the dissemination comes with a slower expertise build up for DiSSCo

- For Distributed Networked:
 - Several members provide and fund recurrent resources to maintain the network.
 - No Single Point of Contact available yet some expertise building albeit at a slow rate.
 - A structure is formed that results in efficiency gains through an active network.
 - The complexity for the hub consists of contact with a group of individuals and following up on the required documents and executing steps.
 - The complexity for all members benefits from leveraging the strengths of specific members for specific tasks in the process (multi national)
- For Ad Hoc Distributed:
 - The decision of who shares in providing and funding the ad hoc resources that are to be delivered is on a case by case basis.
 - The level of expertise will vary and the level of expertise build up will likely be outrun by the changes in the concerning rules and regulations
 - The complexity for the hub consists of contact with all members and following up on the required documents and executing steps.

A PCP goes through stages (Figure 8). The preparation consists of 4 defined stages, the first 2 are the Needs Assessment and Prior Information Notice (PIN), these require input from all the members yet can be coordinated centrally or distributed. The remaining two preparation stages, being Open Market Consultation (OMC) and Innovation Gap, do not require input from all the members. Whether the members need to provide input or not has an impact on the complexity of a stage.

Figure 8. Stages in the pre-commercial procurement process (source: <https://carematrix.eu/pcp-process/>)

The EU provides support in the form of guidance and funding actions, and further guidance can be found on a National or Regional level²³ within some of the Member States. The funding can be split between the preparation stage and the execution stage. The EU considers the open market consultation in the preparation stage of a PCP as an activity that is eligible for funding. The outcome and gained perspective will contribute to the final tender specification.

²³ <https://www.innovatieoverheidsopdrachten.be/europese-oproepen>

Figure 9. Action funded (EU supported) activities in a PCP

(source: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210622.htm>)

For the procurement of the R&D services, the EU guidelines mention 15% of that part of the budget to the Solutions Design, 30% to Prototyping and 55% to Original Development and Operational Testing.

The EU considers the efforts stemming from the procurement of R&D, keeping track of the suppliers progress, evaluation of results, coordination, networking activities and dissemination as eligible activities to allocate to the execution stage of a PCP action. We plot the overall cost and complexity from the point of view of the whole. To combine the cost and complexity of the hub and the members, the amount of participating members and the amount of funding national nodes needs to be taken into account as a factor. We assume more than 170 members to DiSSCo from at least 23 countries (<https://www.dissco.eu/dissco/network/>).

Cost indication on the different approaches

Based on our assumptions, we estimate that the centralised dedicated, centralised delegated and distributed networked approaches represent respectively, 12%, 12% and 92% of the preparation costs of the Ad Hoc model which serves as a reference frame, so at 100%.

overall Cost for PCP preparation

Figure 10. Indicative overall Cost perspective of the preparatory procurement stages

The overall cost is a consequence of the cost spent by the Hub, which is funded via 23 countries, combined with the cost made at the 170+ executing members. So while for the hub the centralised approach represents the biggest cost, in the bigger picture, a centralised action represents a more cost efficient approach (figures 11 & 12).

Figure 11. Indicative Cost for the DiSSCo Central Hub

Figure 12. Indicative Cost for the DiSSCo Members

Complexity Indication on the different approaches

The start-up phase typically benefits from a lower complexity. As an organisation grows into maturity and its activity increases, so will complexity. DiSSCo will start with more than 170 members, providing an exceptional starting complexity.

Based on our assumptions, we estimate that the centralised dedicated, centralised delegated and distributed networked approach represents respectively an index of 15, 16 and 85 of the preparation complexity, where we keep the Ad Hoc model as reference frame at 100.

overall Complexity for pre commercial procurement preparation

Figure 10. Indicative overall Complexity perspective of the preparatory procurement stages

The overall complexity is a consequence of the complexity at the Hub combined with the complexity at the 170+ executing members. So while for the hub the centralised dedicated model represents the biggest complexity, in the overall, centralised action represents a simpler, more transparent and more efficient approach (figures 13 & 14).

Figure 13. Indicative Complexity for the DiSSCo Hub

Figure 14. Indicative Complexity for the DiSSCo Members

06 Recommendation

We recognise that public procurement is a specific undertaking that is governed by legal and regulatory restrictions and obligations. It is important that any procurement team contains or is able to grow expertise and stay updated.

To deliver the expected level of quality (that is to be defined and warranted by the DiSSCo RI), a centralised model is more transparent and straightforward than a distributed model.

While a distributed model would provide all members with a skills development opportunity, the diversity in institutional capacity and staff churn is likely to result in significant fluctuation in the DiSSCo functionality, efficiency and processing time, reflecting on its reputation.

To maximise the impact and output of DiSSCo, dedicated centralised resources appear the straightforward route to achieve the highest quality and build up expertise in favour of the consortium. Nevertheless, dedicating resources is a consideration to be made case by case, especially in the start-up phase of any organisation where it is key to maximise the start-up resources.

A start-up recommendation is to **design the function centralised but to delegate the work during the start-up phase to a member organisation that has the specific capability and expertise or to outsource it to a specialist contractor to cover the central dedicated role *ad interim*.**

This assumes one of the members has the expertise available in house and would be temporarily able to provide the service. Temporarily because we assume a rotation of the delegate function between the members, and before dedicating a resource in the hub a few criteria should be met, such as a minimum workload (to justify dedicated resources), and an increased need for internal perspective and expertise (“institutional memory”). The more the DiSSCo goods and services catch on in the market, and a steady stream of revenue and volume is reached, the more a dedicated resource becomes justifiable.

If however, there is **no relevant expertise found amongst the members, the investment in central learning and the expertise built up at the Hub could be justified from the start.** A lot depends on the terms of the delegated centralised function, how long will the appointment last, can the level of quality in training be warranted across all members, etc.

Once a legal entity, DiSSCo can start to engage in development that leverages the PCP framework. Therefore, **our recommendations to the Construction Master Plan** are the following:

- First, to identify PCP and PPI expertise within the consortium members procurement teams.
- Second, to clarify if the funded fixed cost can include a central procurement resource.
- Third, to define concrete executional steps of the chosen approach for readiness by the launch of DiSSCo as a legal entity.

In a parallel survey of business development professionals in the member organisations, dedicated marketing and procurement functions were seen as potential opportunities for efficiency (finance, effort and resource) gains to be made for DiSSCo and within the DiSSCo member community.

07 Conclusions

Procurement is a key domain for any legal entity. In this report we explore and make recommendations on how buying research and development and innovative products and services could play a key role in improving the efficiency and quality of the future DiSSCo services. **The Roadmap** for the partnerships project within the EU PCP framework starts at **identifying development needs within DiSSCo that exceed the innovative capacity of the consortium**. It leads us along **the strategic check over the gap analysis** via the **support requirements at the DiSSCo Hub and the DiSSCo member institutions** to the following conclusions.

We have established that among the DiSSCo consortium members there exist **unmet innovation needs**. A part of those cannot be covered by the innovative capacity present within the consortium, **requiring external partnerships**. Several of those needs are **in line with the overall strategy** and would be beneficial for DiSSCo, its members, its funders, its clients and society as a whole, if resolved.

We are convinced that **Pre-Commercial Procurement is an opportunity for DiSSCo to advance faster and cheaper on its innovation pipeline**. DiSSCo would benefit from designing for a proactive procurement mentality in the organisation during the DiSSCo Construct phase. We believe the ideal upstream procurement person has affinity with business development and a proactive mindset, on top of reactive data processing skills.

From the insights gained during the efforts on task 4.4, we conclude that **a centralised procurement approach is more favourable, both from a cost as from a complexity point of view**. If the confidence exists that among the members, there is sufficient expertise to manage procurement for DiSSCo, then this should be the approach to start up with. This expertise has to include the processes of pre-commercial procurement and public procurement of innovation. Over time, an evolution towards a dedicated centralised resource can still be made.

However, **to meet the quality and reputation expectations of DiSSCo, an adequate level of PCP/PPI expertise is a must, which if not found among the members, is best integrated directly at the DiSSCo Hub through a dedicated resource (on the payroll or outsourced)**. It is with the same reasoning that we advise against distributed models.

This concludes our efforts for DiSSCo Prepare and lists our recommendation towards the DiSSCo construct phase.

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Annex

Abbreviations

CapEx: Capital Expenditure

CP: Commercial Procurement

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud (<https://eosc-portal.eu/>)

FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable

IRL: Implementation readiness level

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

OpEx: Operational Expenditure

OMC: Open Market Consultation

PCP: Pre-Commercial Procurement

PIN: Prior Information Notice

PPI: Public procurement of innovation

R&D: Research and development

RI: Research Infrastructure

TRL: Technology readiness levels

Glossary

Business Framework: A business framework is a process and fundamental base of what operating strategies guide a business or organisation. A business framework is a process and fundamental base of what operating strategies guide and business or organisation

Capital Expenditure (CapEx): Money invested by a company to acquire or upgrade fixed, physical, non-consumable assets, such as a building, a computer or a new business

Commercial Procurement (CP): The purchase of research services of which all benefits accrue exclusively to the contracting authority or contracting entity, and which it may use in the conduct of its own affairs on condition that it fully remunerates them

Complexity: The state of having many parts and being difficult to understand or find an answer to: a problem of great complexity. complexities [plural] the features of something that make it difficult to understand or find an answer to: There are a lot of complexities surrounding this issue.

Operational Expenditure (OpEx): Money a company spends on an ongoing, day-to-day basis in order to run a business or system. Depending upon the industry, these expenses can range from the ink used to print documents to the wages paid to employees

Open Market Consultation (OMC):As part of the preparation for an innovation driven procurement action, the market consultation involves the proactive analysis of technology offer.

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP):Procurement of research and development of new innovative solutions before they are commercially available. PCP works in conjunction with Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI).

Prior Information Notice (PIN): These are public notices used by government buyers of complex products and services. PINs signal to the wider market that the buyer has a specific upcoming commercial need that will require support from one of more external suppliers.

Public procurement of innovation (PPI): Procurement in which the public sector uses its purchasing power to act as early adopter of innovative solutions which are not yet available on a large-scale commercial basis.

Procurement: The process of finding and agreeing to the terms of a purchase. It includes identifying potential suppliers, negotiating contracts, and selecting the supplier that offers the best value for money. Purchasing is the actual act of buying goods and services.

Public procurement: The process whereby public authorities, including all levels of government and public agencies, buy goods, services or commission work.

Public-Private Partnership: Collaboration between a government agency and a private-sector company that can be used to finance, build, and operate projects, such as public transportation networks, parks, and convention centres

Standard procurement: see commercial procurement

Technology readiness levels (TRL): A method for estimating the maturity of technologies during the acquisition phase of a program. TRLs enable consistent and uniform discussions of technical maturity across different types of technology. TRL is determined during a technology readiness assessment (TRA) that examines program concepts, technology requirements, and demonstrated technology capabilities. TRLs are based on a scale from 1 to 9 with 9 being the most mature technology. The following definitions of TRLs apply, recognising that there are important differences between technological fields:

TRL1 - basic principles observed

TRL2 - technology concept formulated

TRL3 - experimental proof of concept

TRL4 - technology validated in lab

TRL5 - technology validated in relevant environment

TRL6 - technology demonstrated in relevant environment

TRL7 - system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL8 - system complete and qualified

TRL9 - actual system proven in operational environment

Subcontractor description

In WP4, and specifically task 4.2 and task 4.4, we worked with a subcontractor called AcrossLimits, for the expertise needed in the domains of business development and procurement. AcrossLimits is a Maltese registered SME with a long history of successes both on the national and the European stages with participation in over 80 EU funded projects over its 21 years of existence. This history has provided AcrossLimits with a vast network of contacts all over Europe and goodwill within the European Commission for high quality work. Business Innovation is what we do especially when we work with consortia made up of a mixture of public and private organisations that are researching together. We have collaborated in not only building tools to help such economic players but also in running workshops and training to explain to them how best to address the new challenges and opportunities that are found in today's economy.